

Post-Merger Performance of Selected Nigerian Deposit Money Banks-An Econometric Perspective**Author's Details**

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ABSTRACT:

The paper examined post merger performance of Nigerian banking sector with the aim of determining the effect and the extent to which merger influenced bank performance. A judgmental sample technique was used to select 15 listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Data were collected from the published annual reports and account of these banks and were analyzed using percentage and ratios. Multiple regressions were used in testing the hypotheses. The study revealed that there is a strong relationship between bank performance and merger (strategic decisions) – asset profile, capital structure, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and credit risk. That strategic decision has positively influenced bank performance. That on average, bank consolidation resulted into improved performance. The study therefore recommended that the management of the banks should embrace diversification and financial innovation on product strategies as this will help in generating more income for the banks. They should also try to use merger as a strategic tool which must be continuously applied and implemented.

Keywords: Consolidation, Merger, Bank Performance, Asset Profile, Capital structure, Operating Efficiency, Liquidity Risk, Credit Risk.

INTRODUCTION

Banking reforms have been an on-going phenomenon around the world right from the 1980s but it is more intensified in recent time because of the impact of globalization which is precipitated by continuous integration of the world market and economies. Banking reforms involve several elements that are unique to each country based on historical, economic and institutional imperatives. In Nigeria, the reforms in the banking sector preceded against the backdrop of banking crisis due to highly undercapitalization deposit taking banks, weakness in the regulatory and supervisory framework, weak management practices and the tolerance of deficiencies in the corporate governance behavior of banks (Uchendu, 2005).

Banks play a crucial role in propelling the entire economy of any nation, of which there is need to reposition it for efficient financial performance through a reform process geared towards forestalling bank distress. In Nigeria, the reform process of the banking sector is part and parcel of the government strategic agenda aimed at repositioning and integrating the Nigeria banking sector into the African and global financial

system. Towards this end, the sector has undergone remarkable changes over the years in terms of the number of institutions, structure of ownership as well as depth and breadth of operations (Akpan, 2007). These changes have been influenced mostly by the challenges posed by deregulation of the financial sector, operations globalization, technological innovations and implementation of supervisory and prudential requirements that conform to international regulations and standards.

Similarly, a strong and virile economy depends to a very large extent on a robust, stable and reliable financial system including the banking sector. This explains the frequency with which the Nigerian banking sector has witnessed repeated reforms aimed at fine-tuning it to meet the challenges for economic stability and development goals which are not only limited to domestic savings mobilization and financial intermediation but also the elimination of inefficiency to enhance financial efficiency or performance. The performance parameters are determined and measured by return on equity, return on asset and net profit margin.

Statement of the Problem

The recent outbreak of bank mergers and acquisitions in Nigeria is attracting much attention, partly because of heightened interest in what motivates firms to merge and how merger and acquisition affects performance or efficiency. However, this paper investigates effects of post merger performance of banks and explores the sources of any merger-induced changes in performances. It is motivated by the relative dearth of empirical evidence on the impacts of mergers and acquisitions involving Nigerian banks. Overall, the handful of studies on merger and acquisitions (M&A) activities in the Nigerian banking industry provides mixed results. For instance, Mohammed (2005) report that bank mergers taking place in the banking industry do lead on average to improved accounting profitability. Sanni (2009) provide empirical evidence suggestive of limited opportunities for cost savings from large mergers in the banking industry. Olagunju and Obademi (2012) conclude that M&A has contributed immensely to the growth of the real sector of banking.

Overall, all these studies provide mixed evidence and inconclusive evidence which appears counter intuitive and many fail to show a clear relationship between mergers and acquisitions and performance. Against this background, the research is geared towards evaluating the post-merger performance of Nigerian banking sector. In this light, the following objectives are examined.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective is to evaluate the post merger performance of Nigerian banking sector. However the specific objectives are;

- (i) To examine the effects of merger on return of equity of Nigerian banking sector.
- (ii) To assess the effects of merger on return on asset of Nigerian banking sector.
- (iii) To ascertain the effects of merger on net profit margin of Nigerian banking sector.

Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses that were tested in the course of this research are stated below as:

Ho: Merger has no effects on return on equity of Nigerian commercial banks.

Ho: Merger has no effects on return on asset of Nigerian commercial banks.

Ho: Merger has no effects on net profit margin Nigerian commercial banks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mergers and acquisitions are a global business terms used in achieving business growth and survival. Merger entails the coming together of two or more firms to become one big firm while acquisitions the takeover or pursuing similar motives (Amedu, 2004: Bello, 2004: Katty, 2005). Accordingly, Soludo (2004) opined that mergers and acquisitions are aimed at achieving cost efficiency through economies of scale and to diversify and expand on the range of business activities for improved performance.

Many developing countries implemented financial reforms as part of broader market oriented economic reforms since the late 1980s (Uboh, 2005). Globally, activities of banks reflect their unique role as the engine of growth in any economy. The importance of the financial sector of an economy which comprises banks and non-banks financial intermediaries, the regulatory framework and the ever increasing financial products, in stimulating economic growth is widely recognized especially in developmental economics. Uboh (2005) set the pace for the landslide of other works on the interdependent relationship between banks and economic growth.

The Nigerian banking system has undergone remarkable changes over the years, in terms of the number of institutions, ownership structure, as well as depth and breadth of operations. These changes have been influenced largely by challenges posed by deregulation of the financial sector, globalization of operations, technological innovations and adoption of supervisory and prudential requirements that conform to international standards. Prior to the recent reforms, the state of the Nigerian banking sector was very weak. According to Soludo (2004), "the Nigerian banking system today is fragile and marginal. The system faces enormous challenges which, if not addressed urgently, could snowball

into a crisis in the near future. He identified the problems of the banks, especially those seen as feeble, as persistent illiquidity, unprofitable operations and having a poor assets base”.

Imala (2005) posited that the objectives of banking system are to ensure price stability and facilitate rapid economic development. Regrettably these objectives have remained largely unattained in Nigeria as a result of some deficiencies in our banking system, these include: low capital base, a large number of small banks with relatively few branches, the dominance of a few banks, poor rating of a number of banks, weak corporate governance evidence by inaccurate reporting and non-compliance with regulatory requirements, insolvency as evidence by negative capital adequacy ratios of some banks, eroded shareholders fund caused by operations losses, over dependence on public sector deposit and foreign exchange trading and the neglect of small and medium scale private sectors. The Nigerian banking sector plays marginal role in the development of the real sector.

Soludo (2004) opined that, the Central Bank of Nigerian (CBN) chooses to begin the Nigerian banking sector reforms process with the consolidation and recapitalization policy through mergers and acquisitions. This is done in order to arrest systems decay, restoration of public confidence, building of strong, competent and competitive players in the global arena, ensuring longevity and higher returns to investors. These and many more, act as a spring board to achieving improved and enhanced efficiency and financial performance.

Development of the Conceptual Model

In order to guide the researcher, the model consisting of the variables was developed. This framework consisted of both independent and dependent variables. Its diagram is as represented below. The independent variables were asset profile, capital structure, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and credit risk. The dependent variables were return on equity, return on asset and net profit margin.

Fig 1: A framework for determining the Post- Merger Performance of Banks in Nigeria

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization (2013).

METHODOLOGY

The population of this study consists of all the 24 mega banks in Nigeria as at 2010. The judgemental sampling technique was used in selecting the 15 listed banks out of the 24 banks that made the consolidation dead line of 2005. These banks were considered because they are listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange market which therefore enabled us to have easy accessibility to their annual reports which is the major source of our secondary data. The author went ahead to examine and analyze the books of these selected banks.

Data (secondary) were extracted from the financial records of ten years; comprising five-year financial record before the consolidation exercise (i.e. 2001-2005) and five-year financial records after consolidation exercise (i.e. 2006-2010). In analyzing the data, the Pearson's correlation was used to measure the degree of association between variables under consideration while the formulated hypotheses were tested with use of multiple regression analysis.

Measurement of Variables

Bank performance is the dependent variable. The proxies used for this are accounting measures of performance; return on equity (ROE), return on asset (ROA) and net profit margin (NPM) as identified by First Rand Banking Group (2006). Return on equity is how well a company used reinvested earning to generate additional earning. This was measured as profit before tax divided by total equity, return on assets was measured as profit before tax divided by total assets while net profit margin was measured by profit before tax divided by Gross Earnings.

The independent variables (Assets profile, capital structure, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and credit risk) are the strategic decisions that influence bank performance. Asset profile

considered by the ratio of total loan composition and was measured by the ratio of total loan to total asset. Capital structure shows banks strategy regarding their capital structure, measured as the ratio of total equity to total asset.

Operating efficiency otherwise known as cost controlling strategy shows the emphasis to minimize cost by relating expenditure to returns and it was measured by total operating expenses divided by total operating income. Liquidity risk referred to bank’s strategy towards managing liquidity risk and was measured by total loan to total deposit while credit risk which referred to bank’s asset quality was measured as the level of loan loss provisions divided by total loan. The information regarding these variables is as below:

Table 1: Study Variables

Variables	Formula
Return on Equity (ROE)	Profit before tax/Total Equity (PBT/TE)
Return on Asset (ROA)	Profit before tax/Total Asset (PBT/TA)
Net Profit Margin (NIM)	Profit before Tax/Gross Earning (PBT/GE)
Asset Profit (AP)	Total Loan /Total Assets (TL/TA)
Capital Structure (CS)	Total Equity/Total Assets (TE/TA)
Operating Efficiency (OE)	Operating Expenses/Operating Income (OE/OI)
Liquidity Risk (LR)	Total Loan/Total Deposit (TL/TD)
Credit Risk (CR)	Provision for Loan Loss/Total Loan (PLL/TL)

Source: Researcher’s Conceptualization (2013)

Model Specification

To determine the relationship between bank performance and merger of banks in Nigeria, we developed three simple definitional models to guide our analyses. These models are as follows:

Model 1

ROE= f (CS, LR, CR)

ROE = β0 + β1CS+ β2LR+ β3CR + μ---- (1)

Model 2

ROA = f (AP, CS, LR, CR)

ROA = β0 + β1AP + β2CS + β3LR + β4CR + μ---- (2)

Model 3 NPM = f (AP, CS, OE, LR, CR).

NMP = β0 + β1AP + β2CS + β3OE+ β4LR + β5CR + μ---- (3)

Where;

ROE, ROA and NPM represent bank performance variables which are Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Asset and Net Profit Margin. AP, CS, OE LR and CR represent Asset Profile, Capital Structure, Operating Efficiency, Liquidity Risk and Credit Risk respectively while μ represents the error term which accounts for other possible factors that could influence ROE, ROA and NPM that are not captured in the model.

RESULT and DISCUSSION

Tables 2 and 3 below depicted the descriptive statistics of the pre and post merger performance and strategic decisions of 15 listed Nigerian commercial banks in aggregate. With regards to post merger performance of the banks, there is an increase in post merger return in equity, return on asset and net profit margin they have pre merger ROE of 0.16, ROA of 0.02 and NPM of 0.19 while post merger ROE is 0.27, ROA is 0.04 and NPM is 0.28 respectively. This shows an improvement in performance.

Regarding their asset profile, the post merger mean of 0.53 is lower than pre merger of 0.61.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Pre Merger Performance

Variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Return on Equity	75	0.01	0.49	0.16	0.10
Return on Asset	75	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.01
Net Profit Margin	75	0.03	0.39	0.19	0.09

This decrease shows that there is a better post-merger performance with the use of management of assets in relation to total loans. The capital adequacy ratio shows that post merger of 0.19 is greater than pre merger of 0.1, this reveals the agenda of the banking reform that made banks to beef up their minimum capital base to #25 billion naira.

The cost controlling which is operating efficiency shows decline in post merger. This indicates that generally new banks embraced a low cost strategy which may be through economies of scale driving from synergies.

The liquidity risk strategy shows a better liquidity management of the merged banks. The mean liquidity ratio decreased from 0.62 to 0.39 after the merger. Credit risk showed a better post merger performance indices indicate that the merged banks were able to hedge against their credit risk and have a better post merger asset profile that enhances performance.

Asset Profile	75	0.13	0.61	0.35	0.10
Capital Structure	75	0.02	0.22	0.11	0.04
Operating Efficiency	75	0.32	0.99	0.68	0.15
Liquidity Risk	75	0.30	0.98	0.62	0.17
Credit Risk	75	0.01	0.34	0.10	0.08
Valid N (listwise)	75				

Source: Researcher's Analysis (2013)

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Post Merger Performance

Variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Return on Equity	75	0.02	0.61	0.27	0.13
Return on Asset	75	0.01	0.27	0.04	0.03
Net Profit Margin	75	0.02	0.79	0.28	0.14
Asset Profile	75	0.02	0.53	0.26	0.10
Capital Structure	75	0.03	0.50	0.19	0.08
Operating Efficiency	75	0.15	0.95	0.51	0.18
Liquidity Risk	75	0.03	0.64	0.39	0.14
Credit Risk	75	0.09	0.52	0.18	0.14
Valid N (listwise)	75				

Source: Researcher's Analysis (2013)

Regression Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

In this section we used regression analysis to evaluate the post merger performance of Nigerian banking sector. In doing this, we used three simple definitional models.

Table 4 shows the regression analysis for merger and bank performance. The variables involved are credit risk, liquidity risk, capital structure and return on equity. The result presents the effect of Merger on performance of Nigerian banks. The result showed that, calculated t-statistics ($t = 3.518, -2.529$ and 3.276) for parameters capital

structure, liquidity risk and credit risk respectively is greater than tabulated t-statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

The result of the study showed that capital structure and credit risk are significantly having positive relationship with return on equity. So when banks have increase in capital structure and credit risk there would be increased in performance. The result also indicated that when banks are experiencing decreased in liquidity risk there would be increased in performance, since there is a negative relationship between liquidity risk and return on equity.

The coefficient of determination (R^2 is 0.608) indicating that capital structure, liquidity risk and credit risk account for 60.8% of variation in the performance (return on equity) of banks in Nigeria. The remaining 39.2% unexplained variable is largely due to variation in other variables outside the regression model which are otherwise included in the stochastic error term. The overall regression model is statistically significant in terms of its overall goodness of fit ($f = 5.867$, $P < 0.05$). As a result of this, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_1) meaning that merger has significant effects on return on equity of Nigerian commercial banks.

Table 4: Regression Results showing the effect of Merger on Banks Performance (Return on Equity)

Variables	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
Constant	0.249	4.676	0.000
Capital Structure	0.385	3.518	0.001*
Liquidity Risk	-0.468	-2.529	0.014*
Credit Risk	0.347	3.276	0.002*
Goodness of Fit:			
R^2	0.608		
Adjusted R^2	0.605		
F-value	5.867		

*Significant at 0.05 level.

Source: Data Analysis, 2013.

Table 5 shows the regression analysis for merger and bank performance. The variables involved are credit risk, liquidity risk, capital structure, asset profile and return on asset. The result presents the effect of Merger on performance of Nigerian banks. The result showed that, calculated t-statistics ($t = -0.863, 3.276, -2.580$ and 3.292) for parameters asset profile, capital structure, liquidity risk and credit risk respectively is greater than tabulated t-statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

The result of the study showed that capital structure and credit risk are significantly having positive relationship with return on asset. So when banks have increase in capital structure and credit risk there would be increased in performance. The result also indicated that when banks are experiencing decreased in asset profile and liquidity risk there would be increased in performance, since there is a negative relationship between asset profile, liquidity risk and return on asset.

The coefficient of determination (R^2 is 0.684) indicating that asset profile, capital structure, liquidity risk and credit risk account for 68.4% of variation in the performance (return on asset) of banks in Nigeria. The remaining 31.6% unexplained variable is largely due to variation in other variables outside the regression model which are otherwise included in the stochastic error term. The overall regression model is statistically significant in terms of its overall goodness of fit ($f = 4.567$, $P < 0.05$). As a result of this, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_2) meaning that merger has significant effects on return on asset of Nigerian commercial banks.

Table 5: Regression Results showing the effect of Merger on Banks Performance (Return on Asset)

Variables	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
Constant	0.042	2.606	0.011
Asset Profile	-0.095	-0.863	0.001*
Capital Structure	0.347	3.276	0.002*
Liquidity Risk	-0.491	-2.580	0.012*
Credit Risk	0.350	3.292	0.002*
Goodness of Fit:			
R^2	0.684		
Adjusted R^2	0.622		
F-value	4.567		

*Significant at 0.05 level. Source:

Source: Data Analysis, 2013.

Table 6 shows the regression analysis for merger and bank performance. The variables involved are credit risk, liquidity risk, operating efficiency, capital structure, asset profile and net profit margin. The result presents the effect of Merger on performance of Nigerian banks. The result showed that, calculated t-statistics ($t = -3.684$, 11.024 , -5.936 , -3.207 and 7.560) for parameters asset profile, capital structure, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and credit risk respectively is greater than tabulated t-statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

The result of the study showed that capital structure and credit risk are significantly having positive relationship with net profit margin. So when banks have increase in capital structure and credit risk there would be increased in performance. The result also indicated that when banks are experiencing decreased in asset profile, operating efficiency and liquidity risk there would be increased in performance, since there is a negative relationship between asset profile, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and net profit margin.

The coefficient of determination (R^2 is 0.810) indicating that asset profile, capital structure, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and credit risk account for 81.0% of variation in the performance (net profit margin) of banks in Nigeria. The remaining 19.0% unexplained variable is largely due to variation in other variables outside the regression model which are otherwise included in the stochastic error term. The overall regression model is statistically significant in terms of its overall goodness of fit ($f = 3.867$, $P < 0.05$).

As a result of this, the study accepts the alternative hypothesis (H3) meaning that merger has significant effects on net profit margin of Nigerian commercial banks.

Table 6: Regression Results showing the effect of Merger on Banks Performance (Net Profit Margin)

Variables	Coefficients	t-value	p-value
Constant	0.263	2.890	0.005
Asset Profile	-0.513	-3.684	0.000*
Capital Structure	0.935	11.024	0.000*
Operating Efficiency	-0.183	-5.936	0.000*
Liquidity Risk	-0.133	-3.207	0.002*
Credit Risk	0.381	7.560	0.000*
Goodness of Fit:			
R ²	0.810		
Adjusted R ²	0.802		
F-value	3.867		

*Significant at 0.05 level. Source:

Source: Data Analysis, 2013.

CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper attempted to examine the post merger performance of Nigerian banking sector. The result showed an improved post merger financial performance of Nigerian commercial banks. This was evident with the F-test statistic results of the selected banks. Output depicted an increased in their combined means for return on equity, return on asset and net profit margin. The result of these findings was buttressed by De-Nicolo et al (2003)

which is of opinion that merger and acquisitions in the financial system could impact positively on both the financial and operational efficiency of most banks and also Osho (2004) found that banks significantly improved their profit efficiency after mergers. The study concluded that there is an improved performance on the part of selected commercial banks. This in terms return on equity, return on asset and net profit margin as the calculated F-values are greater than the critical value at 5% level of significant. The study

revealed that there is a strong relationship between bank performance and merger (strategic decisions) – asset profile, capital structure, operating efficiency, liquidity risk and credit risk. That strategic decision has positively influenced bank performance. That on average, bank consolidation resulted into improved performance. The finding in this paper is quite in agreement with the work of Umoren (2007) and Sanni (2009). Therefore, the paper recommends that banks should be more aggressive in financial products marketing to increase financial efficiency for an improved financial position. That the management of the banks should embrace diversification and financial innovation on product strategies as this will help in generating more income for the banks. They should also try to use merger as a strategic tool which must be continuously applied and implemented.

Man power training and re-training is a must for all banks. Investment in information technology acquisition, deployment and training to reflect a commitment to leverage new technologies for the benefit of every sophisticated client that are getting wiser on daily basis in Nigeria need not be over-emphasized.

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APPENDIX

List of Banks used for the Study

1. Access Bank Plc
2. Diamond Bank Plc
3. Eco Bank Plc
4. Fidelity Bank Plc
5. First Bank of Nig Plc
6. FCMB Plc
7. GTB Plc
8. Skye Bank Plc
9. Stanbic Bank Plc
10. Sterling Bank Plc
11. Union Bank Plc
12. UBA Plc
13. Unity Bank Plc
14. Wema Bank Plc
15. Zenith Bank Plc